

RECORDING CETACEAN SOUNDS IN THE GERLACHE STRAIT (WEST ANTARCTIC PENINSULA) USING AN AUTONOMOUS TOWED HYDROPHONE RECORDER

O. Savenko^{1,2}, ***V. Tkachenko***^{1,2,3}

¹*State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; o.v.savenko@gmail.com;*

²*Institute of Marine Sciences, University of California Santa Cruz, Santa Cruz, CA, USA;*

³*Pryazovskyi National Nature Park, Melitopol, Ukraine*

Passive acoustic surveys using towed acoustic recorders could provide an additional data source, either in conjunction with or as an alternative to visual sighting surveys for studying cetacean distribution. In February-April 2023, and in March 2024, a SoundTrap 300 HF (Ocean Instruments) hydrophone recording system, encased in a streamlined, flooded housing, was towed from the M/V *Plancius* and R/V *Noosfera* in the Gerlache Strait (West Antarctic Peninsula) to record the sounds of cetaceans. Recordings were made at a distance of 180 m from the vessels within the 0.05–280 kHz frequency range. The 23 hours of recordings were analysed to identify acoustic detections of cetacean species. The audio files were processed using Cornell Lab Raven Pro v1.6.5 software, along with the open-source Pamguard 2.1.5 software. CRAN packages for R software were utilized for statistical analysis and visualisation. During data processing, it was discovered that the vessel's echosounder signals produce a significant amount of interference and echo harmonics throughout the entire frequency spectrum in the recordings. This considerably complicates the extraction, visualization, and structural analysis of the signals. Nevertheless, we were able to identify some of them. All acoustic recordings were categorised, and for the high-quality recordings, the duration of each signal, as well as its amplitude, frequency range, occurrence rates, and sequence, were evaluated. The identified cetacean sounds belonged to the killer whale (*Orcinus orca* (Linnaeus, 1758)), Arnoux's beaked whale (*Berardius arnuxii*, Duvernoy, 1851), Antarctic minke whale (*Balaenoptera bonaerensis* Burmeister, 1867), and humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae* (Borowski, 1781)). We identified whistles, echolocation clicks, and pulsed calls recorded for toothed whales. The sounds of killer whale vocalisations were the most prevalent. In comparison to all other signals, killer whale whistles were of the highest quality and will be utilized in the future for structural analysis to ascertain the ecotype of the individuals to which they belong. The low-frequency sounds of the baleen whales were most affected by the vessel's echosounder. Passive acoustic surveys using towed acoustic recorders have demonstrated their effectiveness as a research method, achieving a high frequency of cetacean sound recordings, including at night when visual recordings were impossible to obtain. It is beneficial to continue utilizing this method across various platforms. For short- and medium-distance surveys, motor boats are preferable due to their absence of a powerful echo sounder and high mobility.